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Oscillating Wave Surge Converter**

Collaborative project

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Dissemination Plan

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

MegaRoller is a Horizon 2020 project focusing on how to improve European Ocean Wave Energy devices, specifically by developing a Power Take-off unit able to increase the output from the few 100 kW range to a full 1 MW range. The project will generate extensive know-how in the area of PTO design and control systems, with the aim to decrease the levelized cost of energy (LCOE) of next generation OWSC devices.

The aim of this dissemination plan is to maximize the impact, take-up, visibility, and credibility of the project. This plan addresses the purpose of dissemination, what will be disseminated to whom, how and when.

The findings from the project will be disseminated to relevant stakeholders throughout the duration of the project. We envisage that this plan is a dynamic document; so that our activities outlined may be subject to change over the duration of the project, and we remain open to alternative ways of publicising and disseminating our results. Dissemination will take place using both traditional channels (publications and conferences) but also in dedicated workshops and scientific meetings, such as in side-events in order to increase the impact of the project.

The communication plan (information about the action), the exploitation and innovation management aspects are all dealt with in separate deliverables and will therefore not be discussed in depth in this dissemination plan.

1 DISSEMINATION OVERVIEW

1.1 Introduction

Wave power represents a considerable opportunity for clean renewable energy supply. The potential of supplying 10-15% of EU power demand by 2050, which can reduce EU dependency on energy imports, create thousands of jobs, and contribute to diversification and decarbonisation of the economy. This project focus on oscillating wave surge converters (OWSCs), a type of wave power technology that is designed to absorb wave energy through the horizontal motion of the prime mover. This deliverable presents the plan for the dissemination of the results that to foster adoption within the ocean energy industry.

1.2 Dissemination objectives

Dissemination is a key activity in MegaRoller in order to increase the impact of the project. The overall objective for dissemination is to maximize the impact, take-up, visibility and credibility of the project. In particular, the specific objectives are:

- Transfer knowledge of the MegaRoller concept through relevant educational resources and the organisation of workshops to relevant stakeholders, authorities, users, suppliers and potential owners of wave energy systems.
- Design, develop and regularly update a dedicated MegaRoller website with relevant material suited for dissemination (reports, white papers, publications, data, blogs, newsletters etc.).
- Support the development of a plan for the exploitation of the key outcomes of the MegaRoller project beyond the life of the project.
- The priorities of the dissemination activities of the MegaRoller project is to promote not only the project results but also Wave Energy as a viable and future energy source in abundance in Europe and around the world.

This way, the MegaRoller project will obtain the attention and support of not only to those who benefit from its advanced technology, but also those who are interested in the topic of wave energy in general, in particular, academia and industry. Many of the dissemination and communication activities are overlapping, and the D6.1 Communication Plan supplements many of the outreach activities towards relevant stakeholders, in particular, society at large and public authorities.

1.3 Dissemination Strategy

With the objective to ensure an effective dissemination of knowledge during the project and beyond, the MegaRoller Consortium has established a Dissemination strategy that is based on the guidelines proposed by the H2020 online manual. The following summaries the dissemination framework set up for MegaRoller project that is suggested in H2020 online manual:

- What dissemination outputs will be created in MegaRoller? See section 2.
- Why dissemination outputs will be created? What is the target that MegaRoller would like to achieve through the dissemination of results? See section 1.2 Objectives.
- Who are the stakeholders of MegaRoller results? See section 4.
- How to disseminate the results? Which channels and tools should be implemented to disseminate the results? See section 5.
- Where will the outputs be made available during and after the project? See section 6
- Who should be in charge of specific dissemination activities in MegaRoller? And

- When the dissemination activities will happen? See section 8

These frameworks are used to establish the dissemination plan. In the following, each point mentioned above is covered in more detail.

2 WHAT WILL BE DISSEMINATED

The project will disseminate the open results from the MegaRoller project. During the project, the focus will be on a combination of continuous dissemination and collaboration with relevant stakeholders to develop a PTO system that will form the core of a new group of European Wave Energy devices. These will, in turn, contribute to enabling a European leadership in Wave Energy and to support the knowledge and competence needed in the industry.

Dissemination can take place in many settings and through various channels. In the following the most common dissemination materials are summarized in separate categories;

2.1 Website

The main goal of the [MegaRoller](#) website is to establish a widespread channel to disseminate and access information around the EU MegaRoller project, activities and results. The target group is a wide set of the stakeholders i.e. Private industry, the scientific community, public authorities, and society at large. Visitors will find public deliverables produced during the project. The web site provides access to internal pages, which is restricted to partners in the project, this mainly aims to facilitate the exchange of documents between the partners but it will be a repository of material that can be relevant for all the partners.

You are here: MegaRoller > Dissemination

Dissemination

All scientific publications will be uploaded to an open repository.

Figure 2-1 Homepage of dissemination on MegaRoller

2.2 Scientific publications

Articles in peer reviewed journals are scientific publications. According to H2020 Open Access Mandate, the MegaRoller project will ensure open access to all scientific publications. Open access refers to the practice of providing online access to scientific information that is free of charge to the end-user and reusable. There are two ways of achieving open access:

- **Green open access:** the author deposits the final peer-reviewed manuscript (not the published version) in an online repository. Most journals request an embargo period before the manuscript can be open access. The H2020 Open Access mandate accepts a maximum of 6 months embargo.
- **Gold open access:** the article is immediately published in open access mode, either by an open access journal or a hybrid journal. Gold open access usually involves Article Processing Charges (APC). The APC should be covered by the corresponding author's institution and are eligible for reimbursement during the project period.

The author decides where to publish. The list below is scientific journals relevant to the MegaRoller project. The list is not exhaustive, and more journals will be considered and added as the work proceeds.

Table 2-1 List of relevant scientific journals

Title	ISSN	Scopus Cite Score	Type of journal	APC ¹	Embargo
Renewable Energy	0960-1481	5,38	Subscription/Hybrid	USD 3000	24 months
International Journal of Neural Systems	1793-6462	5,15	Subscription/Hybrid	Depend on the subject area/ length of the article	12 months
PLoS Computational Biology	1553-734X	4,49	OA	USD 2350	
Frontiers in Marine Science Journal of Marine Science and Engineering	2296-7745 2077-1312	2,89	OAOA	US1900 CHF 350	
Journal of Ocean Engineering and Marine Energy	2198-6452	1,85	Subscription/Hybrid	USD 3000	12 months

All scientific publications will be uploaded to an open repository. The MegaRoller project will use Zenodo as its repository both for publications and research data. A [MegaRoller community in Zenodo](#) has been established. Scientific publications and underlying data will be linked using persisting identifiers.

We assume that new demands on Open Access as expressed in Coalition S² does not affect the MegaRoller project, but the project nevertheless aims to publish in high quality open access journals or platforms where they exist.

Open Access to research data is referred to 6.4 Data management plan.

¹ APC refer to the costs of immediate open access to articles (Gold open access). Green open access can be considered if the journal embargo period doesn't exceed 6 months.

² [cOAlition S : Making Open Access a reality by 2020](#)

2.3 Scientific presentations and industry events/conferences

Several of the industry partners will promote their activity and possible innovations made in industry events. There will also be an extensive participation and presentation of results from MegaRoller in scientific conferences. See Table 5-2 for a detailed list of events.

2.4 Standardization work

Standards can be a powerful tool and an important basis for development. A standard can set certain limitations and requirements that have to be fulfilled or otherwise a unit or system cannot be employed in the market as certifications, in general, will require compliance with standards. Participation in standardization is a way of disseminating the practical results of the work in the MegaRoller as the standards bodies often lack relevant data to support the standardization work.

2.5 Tutorials and educational materials

As a measure to reach a wider audience, including academia and students, technical memos and tutorials including whitepapers will be considered for release through the web page.

2.6 Dissemination reports

Two dissemination reports are planned to be issued at months 18 and 36 respectively, summarizing the activities in Dissemination throughout this period and – if relevant – update on details on planned dissemination. Dissemination plan and report are public deliverables.

2.7 Project Video

A project video is planned to be made during the project. The purpose of the video is to inform the broader audience about the project concept, its goals and possible impacts on the society. The format (animations vs real images) etc will be decided later. The video will have a format and length that makes it suitable for wide distribution, including channels like YouTube. It is also referred to 6.1 Communication plan regarding these types of media use.

2.8 Other

When relevant the MegaRoller consortium will consider if there is an ample opportunity to join forces with another ongoing project, including infrastructure promoting actions. Another action that can benefit from the interaction is the newly started COST action on marine energies, CA 17105 which will cover several aspects of relevance to MegaRoller. Several of the member countries will contribute and the consortium is also represented in the management committee of this cost action.

3 TO WHOM: STAKEHOLDERS IN MEGAROLLER

With the view to have a far-reaching impact in MegaRoller, the dissemination strategy will encompass all stakeholders of the value network. The main stakeholders are:

- Private industry: Utilities, Subsystem suppliers, Engineering, Procurement and Construction companies, Investors, insurers
- Scientific Community: Wave energy researchers, Environmental impact researchers
- Public authorities: National and regional authorities, European Commission
- Society at large: Media and general public

An overview is shown in Table 3-1.

Table 3-1 Overview of stakeholder issues that are addressed in MegaRoller

Category	Target Audience	Why	What's in it for this audience? Issues.
Private Industry	Utilities	There is a lack of practical experience and performance data collected from open sea deployment, preventing industrial stakeholders to develop full-scale arrays	Learn from practical experience and collected performance data to plan for grid integration, operation, and maintenance of wave energy plants
	Subsystem Suppliers		Learn from practical experience and collected performance data in order to improve the performance, reliability, and survivability of subsystems
	Engineering, Procurement and Construction companies	The development of the sector depends on how confident the investors are that the ocean energy devices will perform reliably and produce the expected output for their devices	Learn from practical experience and collected performance data to plan for the construction of wave energy plants
	Investors Insurers		Produce LCOE models and investment business cases based on the data collected in the project
Scientific Community	Wave energy researchers	Models that have been developed only consider the first-generation wave power plants	Access for scientific data and publications of second generation wave energy performance
	Environmental impact researchers		
Public Authorities	National and Regional authorities	Public funding authorities must use stage gate evaluation to allocate funding effectively	Provide a framework to address environmental and social impacts and a case example of a wave energy converter development
	European Commission		
Society at large	Media	Media has so far provided more coverage to more mature sectors (wind and solar)	Provide valuable scientific data to raise awareness about the enormous potential of ocean energy
	General Public		

4 HOW: DISEMMINATION ACTIVITIES

There is a very close link to the communication activities in the project covered in the deliverable D6.1: Communication Plan. While the communication activities main goal is to inform about the action, the project goals, and overall scientific content, the core goal of the dissemination activities is to promote the results of the action. However, some channels, including blogs, press releases, action/project web page all play a part in the promotion of the action itself and there is naturally overlap in some activities and descriptions as both tasks will include information about the action as well as the results. Table 4-1 shows an overview of the planned activities in MegaRoller related to the dissemination.

Table 4-1 Overview of general dissemination activities during MegaRoller

Purpose	Activity	Stakeholder/target group
Share results in order to the industry to learn from practical experience and collected performance data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Articles in industry specific magazines and newsletters Internal channels such as company magazines/conferences Industry events such as exhibition and conferences Research blogs and newsletters* Press releases* Website* Video* 	Private industry
Share results openly in order to the scientific community to access a reference testing facility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Peer-reviewed articles in open access journals Posters and presentations at relevant scientific conferences Scientific work-shops Research blogs and newsletters* Website* Video * 	Scientific community
Raise awareness about the enormous potential of ocean energy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Workshops Involvement in relevant EU implementation plans Blogs and newsletters* Video Social media* 	Public authorities
Raise awareness about the enormous potential of ocean energy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> For all details see deliverable D6.1: Communication Plan 	Society at large

*For more details see deliverable D6.1: Communication Plan.

5 WHERE: DISSEMINATION EVENTS AND ARENAS

Organization and participation of events, which will be thematically related with MegaRoller, will be a cornerstone in the dissemination activities. The events include relevant conferences, seminars, workshops, etc. The main goal of these events is to increase the visibility of MegaRoller results and facilitate knowledge sharing that can accelerate the development of the wave energy industry. Moreover, with the participation of such events MegaRoller project aims to:

- Exchange experience on developing the new PTO with other working groups in the field to join forces and converge into a more standardized solution for wave energy.
- Disseminate the fundamental knowledge, and methodologies developed during the project within the scientific community.
- Facilitate the exchange of standards/guidelines within industrial partners that can help to accelerate a more successful commercial, and non-commercial, exploitation of the project outcomes.

Dissemination results will be carried out through several events during the project. These include events organized by MegaRoller project, such as MegaRoller workshops to introduce MegaRoller PTO and demonstrate its operation in the test bench, and several presentations in relevant conferences within the different areas of interest to the project.

The stakeholder workshops are planned to last one working day and will include presentations, a tour of facilities and Q&A sessions. Participation will be on the invitation. In these sessions, the stakeholders will learn about the project, the technology and the potential benefits of MegaRoller to their respective organisations. A first stakeholder workshop is planned in Month 28 and will focus on renewable energy technology developers while a workshop planned in Month 32 will target potential customers, members of standards working groups and government representatives and press. Table 5-1 summarises the expected impact and stakeholders in the MegaRoller workshops.

Table 5-1 MegaRoller workshops

Venue	Expected Stakeholder	Exp. attendance
Workshop at AW-Energy facilities I	Renewable energy technology developers interested in technology transfer	50-100
Workshop at AW-Energy facilities II	Target potential customers, members of standards working groups and government representatives and press.	50-100

Demonstrations at the AW-Energy test facilities as well as presentations to the stakeholders will be a natural part of the full day workshops.

Table 5-2 summarises the potential events that MegaRoller partners could attend during the project period.

Table 5-2 MegaRoller participation events

Venue	Partner involved	Expected Stakeholder	Exp. attendance
MegaRoller workshop	AW-Energy	Renewable energy technology developers	100
MegaRoller workshop	AW-Energy	Potential customers, members of standards working groups and government representatives and press.	100
World Energy Congress	AW-Energy	Key decision makers such as Industry developers, Policy-makers, and Investors.	10,000
The Future of Energy Summit	AW-Energy	Key decision makers such as Industry developers, Policy-makers, and Investors.	2,000
The Energy Executive Forum	AW-Energy	Key decision makers such as Industry developers, Policy-makers, and Investors.	2,000
European Wave and Tidal Energy Conference (EWTEC)	Cruz Atcheson, SINTEF, WavEC	Academia, Research Institutes, and Industry Researchers	1,000
ETIP Ocean workshop	Cruz Atcheson	EU Public Authorities	400
International Conference on Ocean Energy (ICOE)	WavEC, Hydman, Hydroll, AW-Energy	Industry developers, Policy-makers, Investors, Academia, Research Institutes, and Industry Researchers	100
Offshore Energy Exhibition & Conference	Hydman, Hydroll	Key decision makers such as Industry developers, Policy-makers, and Investors.	12,000
Ocean Energy Europe	SINTEF	Industry developers, Policy-makers, and Investors.	400
European Safety and Reliability Conference (ESREL)	VTT	Academia, Research Institutes, and Industry Researchers	500
Probabilistic Safety Assessment & Management conference (PSAM)	VTT	Academia, Research Institutes, and Industry Researchers	1,000
International Conference on Coastal Engineering	UiB	Academia, Research Institutes, and Industry Researchers	2,000
International Joint Conference on Neural Networks	LIN	Academia, Research Institutes, and Industry Researchers	400

6 WHO: INDIVIDUAL DISSEMINATION PLANS FOR PARTNERS

Each partner has its separate dissemination plan and these are as shown in the table below. Table 2 Overview of individual dissemination plans during MegaRoller

Table 4.2 Overview of individual dissemination plans during MegaRoller

Partner	Activities during the project phase
AWE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Organize two MegaRoller workshops that will showcase MegaRoller PTO and demonstrate its operation in the test bench (first workshop for WEC and renewable energy technology developers interested in technology transfer at M28, a second workshop for potential customers, members of standards working groups, government representatives and press at M32) Give three talks in the most influential future energy events, e.g. World Energy Congress, The Future of Energy Summit, The Energy Executive Forum Publish a conference paper in International Conference on Ocean Energy in 2020 Publish press releases when significant project milestones are reached
ABB	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Present project on ABB Power magazine and also through global ABB web site. Publish result as a reference on Renewable Energy Technology on ABB Groups global organization on energy technology seminars and also on the global publication ABB Review.
Cruz Atcheson	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Attend one conference per year, including publishing a conference paper or presentation. Key industry conferences during the project include the European Wave and Tidal Energy Conference (EWTEC) in Naples in 2019 or the International Conference on Ocean Energy (ICOE) in Washington in 2020. Link with the relevant activities related to standardisation work – preliminarily identified platforms may include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The SET ocean energy implementation plan (including Actions 1.6 Standards and guidelines for evaluation of wave energy technologies or 3.1 Development of certification and standards to support the offshore renewable technology sector) Activities under e.g. the ETIP Ocean events (cf. e.g. Research Priorities 2.2 Increase yield with improved PTO or 2.3 Validation of components and sub-systems)
WavEC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Description of the project in WavEC's website and previous activities carried out by WavEC in the context of the WaveRoller technology development in Peniche. (ongoing) 1 journal paper on the LCA results for the MegaRoller final device and comparison with other MRE technologies and other means of electricity generation, to be published in a marine renewable energy dedicated (e.g. Marine Renewable Energy Journal) 1 conference paper on EIA standard methods for nearshore wave energy devices in ICOE or EWTEC conferences, respectively

Hydroll	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participate in at least 3 marine industry events such as the Offshore Energy Exhibition & Conference, International Conference on Ocean Energy and Ocean Energy Europe Events
Hydman	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participate in at least 3 marine industry events such as the Offshore Energy Exhibition & Conference, International Conference on Ocean Energy and Ocean Energy Europe Events
SINTEF	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Publish 1 journal paper "Grid Integration of wave energy farms: Modeling and simulation" at the end of the project, and 1 conference paper per year or presentations per year (reaching 300+ researchers). • Organize a scientific dissemination event at M18 targeting the marine energy research community • Speak at marine energy European events such as European Wave and Tidal Energy Conference (EWTEC) and Ocean Energy Europe (OEE). If possible organize a specific project-related session between M30 and M36.
VTT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Publish 1 journal paper in an international renewable energy sector journal, 2 conference papers on international ESREL and PSAM conferences and 1 paper in the national Automation day conference.
UiB	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Publish 2 journal papers and 1 conference paper • Present the results at the ICCE (International Conference on Coastal Engineering) in 2020
LIN	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Poster contribution at the 27th Annual Computational Neuroscience Meeting in Seattle/US (July 13 -- July 18, 2018): A. Matysiak A. Hajizadeh, N. Härtwich, R. König, P. May: "A mechanistic model explains auditory evoked responses as a reflection of network properties of the entire auditory cortex" • Poster at Bernstein Conference in Berlin/Germany (September 25 -- September 28, 2018): Aida Hajizadeh, Artur Matysiak, Asim H. Dar, Nina Härtwich, Patrick J. C. May, Reinhard König: "Auditory event-related fields emerging from the network structure of the auditory cortex" • Publish 2 open-access journal papers: one on the machine-learning results of the project (International Journal of Neural Systems) and the other on predictive processing in auditory cortex (PLoS Computational Biology). • Present the results at the International Joint Conference on Neural Networks (IJCNN) and publish related conference papers.

7 WHEN: TIMEPLAN FOR DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES

The Dissemination Plan describes relevant activities that will be undertaken to accomplish the goals mentioned above. Even though, dissemination activities will be done continuously during the project. It is important to establish a timeframe for the activity. Timeplan for dissemination can be achieved into three phases:

- **Initial phase.** In this phase is to establish the dissemination plan in M6 which includes the activities, tools, and procedures to facilitate the dissemination process. No specific dissemination output are expected but some dissemination process has started. The website is established and released.
It was important to finish the building of the website at an early stage in order to make dissemination information on the project and the partners available.
- **Intermediate phase.** In this phase, the dissemination will focus on creating awareness of the progress in the project. Specific dissemination outputs are expected. The first workshop for WEC and renewable energy technology developers interested in technology transfer is expected. The project video will be produced at the end of the phase. A dissemination report will be release in M18.
- **Final phase.** In the final stage, most of the dissemination results and output will be ready. It is expected the second workshop for potential customers, members of standards working groups, government representatives and press. A final dissemination report will be released in M36.

Table 7-1 shows a timeline when the activity will occur with the above mentioned stages. It is quite clear that a timeplan is indicative as it will have to fit with external events, the current needs of the project, maturity of results produced and availability of stakeholders. An outline of such is illustrated below. These periods are indicative only.

Table 7-1 Timeplan for dissemination

Task	2018			2019				2020				2021	
	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q1	Q2
	Initial Phase			Intermediate phase				Final phase					
Publications	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Workshops							x						x
Reporting		x					x						x
Video					(X)*				X				
Standardization							X						X

8 SUMMARY

The following table summarizes the dissemination plan.

Table 8-1 Summary of the Dissemination plan

What	Where	By Whom	How	To Whom	Why
Website	URL domain https://www.sintef.no/MegaRoller Project period 3 years	SINTEF is responsible for the website	Uploading open-access material or link to material available.	All the stakeholders	Increased awareness of the MegaRoller project. Show progress and main results Advertise events
Conference presentations and posters	Suitable events	All MegaRoller partners (details in the above section)	Writing papers in relevant events Giving speeches at relevant events	Participants of the events	Shared/Transfer Knowledge in the research community
Scientific publications	Suitable publication	All MegaRoller partners (details in above section)	Submitting paper in relevant publications	All the stakeholders especially researchers	Shared/Transfer Knowledge in the research community
Standardization	Working group reports	AW-Energy	Writing reports	All the stakeholders especially members of standards working groups	Transfer Experience with others developers
End-user workshops	AW Energy facilities	AW-Energy	Presentations, a tour of facilities and Q&A sessions	All the stakeholders especially potential costumers, members of standards working groups and government representatives and press	Demonstration of MegaRoller
Project Video	Web	SINTEF	Producing a project vide	All the stakeholders especially broader audience	Inform the broader audience about the project concept